

AUTO-OXIDATION OF ASCORBIC ACID IN PRESENCE OF VANADIC ACID, MOLYBDIC ACID AND TUNGSTIC ACID SOLS

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The auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid has been studied in presence of vanadic acid, molybdic acid and tungstic acid sols. in the pH range 3.5-4.3. It has been found that (a) vanadic acid sol in all concentrations accelerates the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid and its activity is even greater than that of copper; (b) molybdic acid sol in low concentrations accelerates but in high concentrations inhibits the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid; (c) tungstic acid in all concentrations inhibits the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid.

During the last few years a large amount of work has been done on the physiological action as well as on the various physicochemical properties of ascorbic acid. Herbert and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1270) made for the first time a careful investigation of some of the physicochemical properties of ascorbic acid obtained from nature. Ghosh and Rakshit (*Biochem. Z.*, 1936, 289, 15; 1937, 294, 395; 1938, 297, 153) have made a detailed and thorough investigation on the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid.

The constitution of ascorbic acid as given in (I) is now generally accepted as correct.

The hydroxy groups attached to the double-linked carbon atoms have the remarkable property that they are capable of easy oxidation and stepwise dissociation into H^+ ions. Kellie and Zilva (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 1028), Barron and co-workers (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 112, 625) found that recrystallised natural ascorbic acid, free from the last traces of copper and iron, did not undergo any auto-oxidation up to pH 7.6. Ghosh and Rakshit (*loc. cit.*), however, found that carefully purified synthetic ascorbic acid, when dissolved in purest water, oxidised in air at pH above 3 and at pH range 5.8 to 7.2, 70-90% auto-oxidation took place in an hour. Sulphydril compounds, chlorophyll, amino-acids and alkali cyanides inhibit the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid, while copper and iron were found to be strong catalysts in the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid. Dekker and Dickinson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2165), have studied the oxidation of ascorbic acid by oxygen with cupric ion as catalyst and explained the mechanism of the catalytic activity of copper. Lyman, Schultze and King (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 118, 757) found that the catalytic oxidation of ascorbic acid by copper in presence of meta-phosphoric acid was inhibited. Mawson (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 569) studied the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid in presence of extracts of tissues and found strong inhibition. Giri and Shourie (*Indian J. Med.*,

Res., 1940, 27, 685) found that protective mechanism existing in tissues, which protects ascorbic acid against catalytic oxidation by copper, was mainly confined to the colloidal constituents of the tissues.

The object of the present investigation is to study the influence of inorganic colloids like vanadic, molybdic and tungstic acid sols on the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of Sols.

Vanadic acid sol was prepared by adding to a solution of sodium meta-vanadate a little greater than half the molecular proportion of hydrochloric acid when a reddish yellow sol was produced.

The concentration of the sol is expressed in terms of the concentration of V_2O_5 .

Molybdic acid sol was prepared by adding to a solution of sodium molybdate about twice the molecular proportion of hydrochloric acid when a colourless sol was produced. The concentration of the sol is expressed in terms of the concentration of MoO_3 .

Tungstic acid sol was prepared by adding to a solution of sodium tungstate a little greater than one and a half molecular proportion of hydrochloric acid. The concentration of the sol is expressed in terms of the concentration of WO_3 .

Ascorbic acid solution was prepared each day just before the experiments and its strength checked by iodine titration. The sols were prepared every day two hours before the actual mixtures were prepared.

When ascorbic acid was mixed with vanadic acid sol, the mixture first became green and then it turned to blue very quickly. When ascorbic acid was mixed with molybdic acid sol, a yellow colour was developed which with time became green and then blue. With tungstic acid sol ascorbic acid gave a yellow colour with orange tinge.

Since ascorbic acid is a strong reducing agent, the reactions between ascorbic acid and the sols were first studied. The reaction in each case was adjusted to pH 3.5 by the addition of dilute caustic soda solution. Pure ascorbic acid and the mixture of ascorbic acid and sol were placed separately in two similar flasks which were then filled with nitrogen. The flasks were then shaken in a shaking machine in the dark and the rate of reaction was followed by the decrease in the concentration of ascorbic acid with time. Ascorbic acid was estimated by pipetting out 1 c.c. of the reaction mixture in dilute hydrochloric acid and titrating with iodine solution using starch as indicator. It was found that ascorbic acid could be estimated in presence of reduced vanadic acid sol when dilute acetic acid solution was used instead of dilute hydrochloric acid solution.

TABLE I

 Ascorbic acid = $1 \times 10^{-2} M$. Temp. = 24° . $pH = 3.5$.

Time.	Vol. of iodine solution ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) = 1 c.c. of the reaction mixture.				
	Sol = nil	Vanadic acid ($2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$)	Molybdic acid ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$)	Molybdic acid ($1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$)	Tungstic acid ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$)
0 min.	0.98 c.c.	0.98 c.c.	0.98 c.c.	0.98 c.c.	0.98 c.c.
90	"	0.96	0.97	0.97	0.98

From the above table it is clear that the blue colour of the mixtures is due to the reduction of the sols by 1 or 2 % of ascorbic acid present in the mixture.

The oxidation of ascorbic acid was determined by measurement of the oxygen consumption by the well known Warburg method. One Warburg cell contained only a little water and the reading of the manometer attached to it was subtracted from the readings of the other manometers, in order to eliminate the errors due to changes in the external conditions. The second cell contained pure ascorbic acid solution and the rest contained ascorbic acid solution with sols of different concentrations. Precautions were taken during the course of the experiment to avoid contamination of the solutions by heavy metals. Warburg cells were carefully cleaned and minimum quantity of grease was used for ground joints so that ascorbic acid solution did not come in contact with grease while shaking. Merck's extra pure hydrochloric acid, sodium meta-vanadate, sodium molybdate, sodium tungstate, caustic soda and Light's purest synthetic *L*-ascorbic acid were used throughout the investigation. For making solutions redistilled water was used.

The experiments were carried out at temperatures between 24° and 32° and at pH range 3.5 to 4.3. Each experiment was conducted for 90 minutes and manometer readings were taken at intervals of 30 minutes.

The experimental results are given in Figs. 1—7. Results obtained with vanadic acid sol are illustrated in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. Results obtained with molybdic acid sol are illustrated in Figs. 4, 5 and 6. Fig. 7 gives the results with tungstic acid sol. In Figs. 1—7, volume of solution = 2 c.c., number of oscillations per min. = 120, air = 17 c.c. and amplitude = 8 cm.

From Fig. 1, it will be seen that at pH 4.3 the rate of oxidation of ascorbic acid ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) increases as the concentration of the sol increases from $1.95 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $6.25 \times 10^{-4} M$ and when the concentration of the sol is increased more, the rate of oxidation practically remains constant. When the results in Fig. 1 are compared with the results in Fig. 3, it is evident that as the concentration of ascorbic acid is increased, keeping the concentration of the sol constant, the rate of acceleration of ascorbic acid oxidation is diminished. Curves in Fig. 2 illustrate the effect of lowering the pH of the solutions. At pH 3.7 the activity of the sol in accelerating the oxidation of ascorbic acid is found to be increased.

FIG. 3
Vanadic acid sol.
Temp. = 30°. pH = 4.3.
Ascorbic acid = $5 \times 10^{-3} M$.

FIG. 4
Molybdic acid sol.
Temp. = 24°. pH = 4.3.
Ascorbic acid = $1 \times 10^{-2} M$.

FIG. 5
Molybdic acid sol.
Temp. = 28°. pH = 4.3.
Ascorbic acid = $1 \times 10^{-2} M$.

FIG. 6
Molybdic acid sol.
Temp. = 28°. pH = 3.5.
Ascorbic acid = $1 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Curves in Fig. 4 clearly indicate that at pH 4.3 the rate of oxidation of ascorbic acid ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) increases as the concentration of the sol is decreased from $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ to $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ and when the concentration of the sol is decreased more, the rate of oxidation remains constant. The effect of increasing the concentration

of ascorbic acid keeping the concentration of the sol constant (Figs. 4 & 5) and the effect of lowering the pH of the solutions (Fig. 6) are practically the same as in the case of vanadic acid sol.

At pH 3.5 tungstic acid in all concentrations inhibits the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid and the rate of oxidation of ascorbic acid in presence of the sol increases as the concentration of the sol diminishes (Fig. 7).

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